

Three Horizon Europe projects collaborating to advance sustainable and equitable water governance across Europe.

From 2023 to 2026-27

GOVAQUA

Testing governance tools in Living Labs across Europe

4 Years **11 Partners**

6 Living Labs

RETOUCH NEXUS

Developing Nexus-smart governance approaches

4 Years **13 Partners**

6 Demo Cases

INN WATER

Piloting governance solutions using social innovation

3 Years **13 Partners**

5 Pilot Sites

The Added Value of WaterGovernance2027

Accelerate innovation in sustainable and equitable water governance.

Connect research and practice across diverse European context.

Support EU policy ambitions, including the Green Deal, WFD and SDGs.

The synergy in number

+10 Countries involved

37 Partners across EU

17 Case Studies

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation